

Linear DE for Schrodinger Equation in Lorentz Boosted

Frame?

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For the case of rotations and other situations, one may write the Schrodinger equation in the rotating frame as: $\frac{1}{2m} (-idj - mV_j)(-idj - mV_j) W'(r) - .5mV_jV_j W'(r) + V(r)W'(r) = E' W'(r)$ ((1))

For the rotating case, $V_j = \epsilon_{jlm} r_l (-idm)$. Here $dm = d/dr_m$ where $r_m = x, y$ or z . Equation ((1)) is usually obtained through gauge type arguments similar to those used when dealing with a Lorentz force.

In (1), it is suggested ((1)) follows from a Lorentz boost which is then written in a nonrelativistic approximation. The authors of (1), however, note ((1)) cannot be obtained from a single boost for the case of a rotation. Thus, it seems the Lorentz boost approach may be safely considered for the case of constant V_j i.e. constant boost velocity. In this note, we wish to consider equation ((1)) and some of the ideas of (1) to argue that there seems to be a linear differential equation which gives information about the wavefunction in the boosted frame. This equation does not seem to usually appear in discussions of different frames.

Arguments of (1)

In (1), the authors consider the unitary transformation:

$$S = \exp(-imV_j r_j + im/2 V_j V_j t) \quad ((2))$$

They argue this transformation follows from a Lorentz boost which is then nonrelativistically reduced. They wish to use this transformation to obtain ((1)) which is usually obtained through a gauge approach similar to that used when dealing with the Lorentz force. (In that case, no Lorentz boost is used).

The authors write:

$$H' = S^+ H S \quad \text{where } H = \frac{1}{2m} p^2 \quad ((3))$$

From ((3)), H' is written as $\frac{1}{2m} (p - mV)^2$. In order to obtain this result, it seems that V is being treated as a constant vector. If one adds r dependence, this result does not seem to follow for the case of a rotation for which $V_j = \epsilon_{jlm} r_l \omega_m$ where ϵ_{jlm} is the Levi Civita symbol.

If one uses $H' = S^+ (-id/dt S) + S^+ H S$, the first term yields $-.5mV_j V_j$ leading to an equation of the form of ((1)).

This equation then can be solved to obtain $W'(r', t')$ in the boosted frame.

Interestingly, the authors of (1) show the relationship between the energies in the two frames using the Lorentz transformation:

$$E' = E - V_j p_j + .5m V_j V_j \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } r = r' + V \quad \text{Here } r, r' \text{ and } V \text{ are vectors.}$$

To obtain ((4)) one uses: $E' = (E - \beta_j V_j) / (\sqrt{1 - \beta_j^2})$ ((4b)). The denominator is then expanded and two terms kept.

Time Dependence

Consider $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} = i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} - i V_j \frac{d}{dx}$ as written in (1). If V_j is a constant boost velocity $\frac{d}{dx} = \frac{d}{dx}$.

Next, consider $S^+ i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} S = SW(r,t)$. The first term $S^+ (\frac{d}{dt} S)$ yields $.5mV_j V_j$ which becomes part of H' , but there are still two other terms $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} (\exp(imV_j r_j - im.5 V_j V_j t) \exp(-iEt) W) = (-m.5V_j V_j + E) W'$.

$$\text{Thus: } (E' + V_j p_j) W' = (.5mV_j V_j + E) W' \quad ((8))$$

This is the linear differential equation relating the two frames. Furthermore it reproduces the relationship between E and E' given by special relativity, namely ((4b)).

If V_j is a constant velocity, then ((8)) is of the form:

$V_j i \frac{d}{dx} W' = C_1 W'$ where W' is a constant. For the simple case of $V_j = V_x$ and 0 otherwise, one has:

$$i \frac{d}{dx} W' = C_2 W' \quad \text{or } W' = \exp(i C_2 x) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, the boost adds a phase. Consider next the equation in the boosted frame:

$$\frac{1}{2m} (-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} - V_j)(-i\hbar \frac{d}{dx} - V_j) \exp(-iC_2 x) w' + V(r)W' - .5mV_j V_j W = E' W' \quad \text{Here } W' = \exp(iC_2 x) w'$$

$$\text{Then: } -\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} w' - C_2^2 w' + 2C_2 \hbar \frac{d}{dx} w' - 2C_2 \hbar \frac{d}{dx} w' + V(r)w' = E' w' \quad \text{or}$$

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \hbar^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} w' - C_2^2 w' + V(r)w' = E' w' \quad ((10))$$

This, however, is essentially the Schrodinger equation in the lab frame with a shifted energy. Thus, the Lorentz boost term simply adds the phase factor and creates a shifted energy.

It is not clear how useful the Lorentz boost is for $V_j(r)$. The authors of (1) already note that the single boost approach does not work for a rotating frame and that one may use ((1)) obtained through the usual gauge approach. In the above, we have considered the linear DE ((8)) only for the case of a constant V_j Lorentz boost and so it is not clear if it works in other contexts. In an earlier note, it was shown one could consider a dilating frame generated by $r_j p_j$. It was found that one also had a phase shifted wavefunction in such a case. For curiosity, for a dilation ((8)) would become:

$$(E' + i\hbar r_j \frac{d}{dx}) W' = (-.5m r r + E) W' \quad ((11)) \quad \text{Alternatively, one may write } r_j p_j \text{ as } r p_r. \text{ Then ((11)) may be solved to give:}$$

$W' = \exp(i r r .25/C - i \ln(r) (E - E'))$. The factor $\exp(i r r .25/C)$ is similar to that found by solving ((1)) explicitly for a dilation i.e. $V_j = C r_j$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to examine the ideas of (1) which describe different frames by Lorentz boosts to reproduce equation ((1)) which is normally obtained through a gauge approach (similar to that used for the Lorentz force). We use $V_j = \text{constant}$ in space and find a linear DE which shows a phase factor $\exp(iCx)$ is picked up through the Lorentz boost. We also examine the case of a dilation, out of curiosity, and see that the linear DE yields a phase factor similar to that obtained by solving ((1)) directly.

References

1. Anandan, Jeeva and Suzuki, Jun. Quantum Mechanics in a Rotating Frame 2003.

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/quant-ph/0305081.pdf>